

How Do Carbon Nanotube Fibers Gain Their Strength?

Tsu-Wei Chou

*Center for Composite Materials and Department of Mechanical Engineering University of Delaware,
Newark, Delaware 19716, USA*

The potential of using CNTs in a continuous form would enable their adaptation to many well-developed composites processing, characterization and micromechanics methodologies. The current experimental and analytical research efforts provide fundamental understanding of the electromechanical behavior of CNT fibers and facilitate future optimal design of their performance in multifunctional composites.